

X-ray Investigation of the Crystals of *o*-Nitrodiphenylamine.

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The crystals of *o*-nitrodiphenylamine ($C_6H_5 \cdot NH \cdot C_6H_4NO_2$) have been studied crystallographically and have been found to develop $c\{001\}$, $q\{011\}$, $o\{111\}$ and sometimes $b\{010\}$ faces. They belong to the rhombic bipyramidal class and the axial ratio is

$a : b : c = 0.4678 : 1 : 0.6709$ (Groth, "Chemische Krystallographie," V, p. 49).

The substance was prepared in the laboratory by heating for twelve hours a mixture of *o*-nitraniline (3 g.), bromobenzene (12 c.c.), potassium carbonate (1 g.) and a trace of cuprous iodide which acts as a catalyst (*Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 4545). The excess of bromobenzene was removed by steam distillation and the unacted *o*-nitrodiphenylamine separated as an oil which solidified on cooling. It was purified by repeated crystallisations from alcohol.

The crystals grow in thin hexagonal or rhombic plates from a solution of the substance in alcohol. In the flat face, the angle θ in the hexagonal, and the angles θ and ψ in the rhombic forms of the crystals were measured and their values were found to agree very closely with those calculated from the ratio $a : b$ given above.

FIG. 1.

	Obs.	Cal.
θ	... 130°20'	129°52'
ψ	... 50°17'	50°8½'

This leaves no doubt that the flat face is the $c\{001\}$ face in both the forms of the crystals. The measurement of other interfacial angles showed that the bounding faces are $o\{111\}$ and $q\{011\}$.

TABLE I.

	Fock's obs. values (<i>cf.</i> Groth).	Authors' obs. values.	Values calc. taking $b:c$ $= 1:0.6976$.
$o(111) : o'(111)$ =	$62^{\circ}34'$	$62^{\circ}17'$	$62^{\circ}33'$
$o(111) : o(111)$ =	$42^{\circ}30'$	$42^{\circ}30'$	$42^{\circ}27'$
$o(111) : q(011)$ =	$50^{\circ}39'$..	$50^{\circ}43'$
$q(011) : c(001)$ =	$34^{\circ}53'$	$35^{\circ}8'$	$34^{\circ}55'$
$o(111) : q(011)$ =	$77^{\circ}25'$...	$77^{\circ}22'$

The crystals were examined by the rotation method using a Shearer gas tube and copper anticathode. The rotation photographs (Plates I, II and III) about the three axes gave the following values for the dimensions of the unit cell :

$$a = 6.86\text{\AA}, \quad b = 14.68\text{\AA}, \quad c = 10.21\text{\AA}$$

The axial ratio is

$$a : b : c = 0.4673 : 1 : 0.6956.$$

This ratio when compared with that given by Groth shows a large discrepancy in the value of $b : c$. But on recalculating this ratio from the interfacial angles observed by Fock (*cf.* Groth, *loc. cit.*, p. 49), it is found that

$$b : c = 1 : 0.6976$$

which agrees very well with that found from the X-ray data.

In order to examine the halvings of planes, oscillation photographs were taken about the a , b , c axes and the spots were indexed by means of Bernal's chart (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, **A 113**, 117). The following two tables give the planes observed and a relative idea of their intensity estimated by eye. The notations used have their usual significance,

FIG. 2.

Rotation photographs.

PLATE I
About a -axis
D = 4.04 cm.

PLATE II
About b -axis
D = 4.04 cm.

PLATE III
About c -axis
D = 4.04 cm.

TABLE II.

Axial planes.	Prism planes.	Prism planes.	Prism planes.
	(0kl).	(hol).	(hko).
001 v.s.	011 v.s.	201 s.	120 w.m.
002 m.	012 v.s.	202 m.s.	140 m.
003 w.	013 v.s.	203 m.	160 w.m.
004 w.	021 s.	204 w.m.	180 w.m., m.
005 m.	023 m.s.	401 w.m.	220 w.m.
020 w.	031 s.	402 w.m.	240 w.m.
040 v.w.	032 m.	403 w.	260 w.m.
060 v.w.	041 w.m.	280 w.m.
080 w.	042 w.m.	320 w.m.
200 s.	043 w.m.	340 w.m.
.....	044 w.	360 v.w.
.....	045 v.w.
.....	051 w.m.
.....	052 w.m.
.....	053 w.m.
.....	055 w.
.....	061 w.m.
.....	062 w.m.
.....	063 w.
.....	064 m.s.
.....	071 m.
.....	073 v.w.
.....	081 w.

TABLE III.

General planes.

111 s.	211 s.	311 w.m.
112 s.	212 m.	312 w.m.
113 m.	213 v.w.	321 w.
114 m.	214 w.	322 w.
115 w.m.	215 v.w.	323 w.
121 v.s.	221 w.m.	333 v.w.
122 m.s.	222 m.	341 v.w.
123 m.	223 w.m.	342 w.m.
124 v.w.	224 w.m.	351 v.w.
125 v.w.	225 v.w.	352 v.w.
131 s.	231 w.m.
132 m.s.	232 w.
133 m.	234 v.w.
134 w.	241 v.w.
135 w.	242 w.m.
141 w.m.	243 w.m.
142 m.	244 w.
143 w.m.	251 w.
144 w.m.	252 w.
145 w.	253 m.
151 w.m.	254 v.w.
152 w.m.	261 w.
153 w.m.	262 w.
154 w.m.	263 v.w.
161 w.m.	264 v.w.
162 m.	271 v.w.
163 w.
164 v.w.
172 w.m.

Table I shows that (hol) planes are halved when h is odd, and (hko) are halved when k is odd. These halvings correspond to the space group Q'_h with Γ_0 Bravais lattice (Astbury and Yardley, *Phil. Trans.*, 1924, **A224**, 221). The number of asymmetric molecules per unit cell required by the space group is eight, while the number of molecules of *o*-nitrodiphenylamine (Mol. wt., 214) calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell and the specific gravity of the crystals, which was found to be 1.366, is only four (accurately 3.97). The molecules, therefore, possess some element of symmetry and this

may be a dyad axis of symmetry perpendicular to (001) or a plane of symmetry parallel to (100) or a centre of symmetry.

The molecule of *o*-nitrodiphenylamine is chemically represented as

and it is difficult to see from this representation the likelihood of the existence in the molecule of any of the three elements of symmetry required by the space group. It is possible, therefore, that the molecule of *o*-nitrodiphenylamine is an asymmetric one, in which case it cannot belong to the orthorhombic bipyramidal class, as in none of the space groups of this class, the number of asymmetric molecules required in the unit cell is four. Therefore only two possibilities remain to be considered (i) that the crystals may not belong to the orthorhombic system and (ii) that they may belong to some other group of the orthorhombic system.

(i) In order to decide the first possibility, the crystals were examined under a polarising microscope but no axial figures could be observed from the *c* (001) face. This observation is in agreement with the statement in Groth (*loc. cit.*). However, it is probable that the orthorhombic symmetry determined by goniometric measurements may not be confirmed by the internal arrangement of the molecules in the unit cell and these crystals may belong to the monoclinic system with an angle β differing from 90° by a few seconds. In that case the intensity of (hol) and (hoi) planes should be different from each other. In the planes observed on the oscillation photographs about the three axes, the intensities of (hol) planes were observed to be the same as those of (hoi) planes. However the differences in intensity, if any, may be small and have not been noticed by the eye and can only be discovered if intensity measurements of the spots are made.

(ii) As regards the second possibility the following are the only possible alternatives:

(a) The crystals may belong to the orthorhombic pyramidal class and to point group C_{2v} . On examining the abnormal halvings for those groups of this class which require four asymmetric molecules per unit cell (Astbury and Yardley's tables p. 233) it will be seen that the halvings observed do not correspond to any one of them. However for this class of crystals the symmetry axes *a* and *b* are interchangeable.

On doing this the observed abnormal halvings will be (i) (okl) halved when k is odd and (ii) (hko) halved when h is odd. These halvings also do not correspond to any of those mentioned in the tables.

(b) The crystals may belong to orthorhombic bispheroidal class and to the space group Q . In this class also there are no halvings corresponding to the ones observed in this investigation.

Thus the only possibility is that the crystals belong to the orthorhombic bipyramidal class and to the space group Q_h^1 . In this class of crystals all the three axes a , b and c are interchangeable (Astbury and Yardley's tables p. 231) and the (hol) and (hko) planes in which halvings have been observed can change to the planes shown in the following table in which the corresponding nature of halvings is also indicated.—

TABLE IV.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	(hol)	(okl)	(hko)	(hol)
Halved when	h is odd	k is odd	h is odd	l is odd
	(hko)	(hko)	(hol)	(okl)
Halved when	k is odd	h is odd	l is odd	k is odd

On referring to Astbury and Yardley's tables (pp. 234-235) it will be seen that no condition except (1) is possible. In that case the atoms constituting the molecule of *o*-nitrodiphenylamine are so arranged in the unit cell of the crystal that the molecule possesses one of the symmetry elements characteristic of the group. Consequently the two rings were placed in space in various ways and each arrangement was examined for any possible molecular symmetry. The only arrangement possible is the one in which the two rings are placed in planes parallel to each other and there is a geometrical plane of symmetry passing through the centres of the two nitrogen atoms. The two oxygen atoms of the nitro-group may be situated in any symmetrical position on either side of the symmetry plane. It is necessary to mention here that the carbon atom to which the nitro-group is attached and the one in the geometrically symmetrical position, are not identical with respect to the number of electrons associated with them.